



(a)



(b)



(c)



(d)



(e)



(f)



(g)



(h)

Fig A.1. Diagrams of Fuzzy membership functions. Planting ability of *Corymbia citriodora* (m) - Fuzzy Linear; V12 - Ability to plant *Eucalyptus urophylla* x *Eucalyptus grandis* (m) - Fuzzy Linear; V13 - Ability to plant *Eucalyptus grandis* (m) - linear Fuzzy; V14 - Ability to plant *Eucalyptus urophylla* (m) - Fuzzy small; V2 - Roads (m) - Fuzzy Linear; V3 - Land use and occupation (m) - Fuzzy Linear; V4 - Slope classes (m) - Fuzzy Linear; V5 - Environmentally regulated properties (m) - Fuzzy Linear.

Source: The authors.